

Design and Implementation of Quantum Cellular Automata Based Novel Adder Circuits

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Abstract : The most important mathematical operation for any computing system is addition. Any other operation like multiplication, subtraction, division can be performing by an adder circuit. An efficient adder can be of greater assistance in designing of any arithmetic circuits. Quantum-dot Cellular Automata (QCA) is a promising nanotechnology to create electronic circuits for computing devices and suitable candidate for next generation of computing systems. Investigations on the reduction of QCA majority gates and inverter for various adders are limited, there are very few designs present for reference. As a result implementation of adders using QCA framework is gaining its importance in recent research. The article presents a modest approach to implement a novel XOR gate. This component is suitable for designing many variants of QCA circuits. The gate is simple in structure and powerful in terms of implementing digital circuits. By applying the XOR gate, the hardware requirement for a QCA circuit can be decrease and circuits can be simpler in level, clock phase and cell count. In order to verify the functionality of the proposed device some implementation of Half Adder (HA) and Full Adder (FA) is checked by means of computer simulations using QCA-Designer tool. Simulation results and physical relations confirm its usefulness in implementing every digital circuit.

Keywords : Clock, Computing system, Majority gate, QCA, QCA Designer.

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